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A Comparative Assessment of Cryptography Algorithms for Data Analytics Applications in Smart Metering Systems

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Abstract: With the proliferation of smart meters in smart electric networks, new applications and challenges to the energy sector are brought, mainly with respect to cybersecurity and data privacy. To protect them, a mechanism that helps protect data is necessary, with cryptography being one of the most used. This paper presents a comparison of algorithms that can be used in smart meters to safeguard the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of the data generated by smart meters and that, in turn, are efficient to process in this class of embedded devices.

Keywords: Cryptography, Smart Meter, Smart Metering Systems, IoT, Smart Grid

1. INTRODUCTION

Within the Smart Grid Program (PRODEREI) 2017-2031 of SENER (2017) and in which the Federal Electricity Commission (CFE), the National Center for Energy Control (CENACE) and the Energy Regulatory Commission (CRE) participate, it stipulates that the main objective is the use of digital information and control technology to improve the stability, safety, and efficiency of the National Transmission Network and the General Distribution Networks. □

In addition, PRODEREI (SENER, 2016) stipulates other premises among which the cybersecurity of all the systems stands out. In this sense, smart meters are considered as the first point of attack, so having security mechanisms is a necessity, given that the SG (Smart Grid) is a critical infrastructure of national security.

According to the World Bank, energy theft contributes to the loss of energy delivery by 25% in India, 16% in Brazil, 6% in China and the United States, as well as 5% in Australia (Borges et al., 2013). Energy theft in these countries is often achieved by theft (tapping) in the distribution lines. To detect these changes, electric companies such as BC Hydro have begun to install Smart Meters (SM) on customers (Blokdyk, 2017). However, recently smart meters have begun to be vulnerable to cyber intrusions (Borlase, 2015).

In 2010, the FBI's Cyber Intelligence Section reported that the consumption of smart meters in Puerto Rico was altered, introducing annual losses to electricity companies estimated at 400 million dollars (Sun et al., 2017). In 2014, the BBC News

reported that SM in Spain was "hacked" to reduce the billing of electricity consumption (Weranga, 2014). Since SMs have been compromised, the efforts of utilities such as BC Hydro have only increased the number of energy theft attacks through cybernetic methods (Toledo, 2013).

For the good use of Smart Metering Systems (SMS), it is required, among other things, that smart meters are not susceptible to be modified in terms of their energy consumption, that only people and devices with the necessary credentials can access all the information stored in the device, as well as the transmission of the meter data to other devices, is done reliably and safely (Krishna et al., 2016).

Cybersecurity has been addressed for some years now, but in the field of electrical networks and smart metering systems it is relatively recent, and there are still many opportunities for improvement.

In addition, SMS are generating a vast quantity of data which be must be analyzed for offering more adequate services in SG (Mathiyalagan, et al., 2017).

This work presents a comparison of diverse cryptography algorithms which can be implemented in embedded devices like SMs. The authors present some recommendation about which are the better implementations according to different scenarios, particularly in data analytic applications.

2. CYBERSECURITY IN SMART METERS AND SMART METERING SYSTEMS

2.1 Smart Meters and Smart Metering Systems

SMS are the cornerstone of SMS due to their data processing and communication capabilities that provide new applications to the energy sector.

The SMS are responsible for reporting the energy consumption of customers as well as deriving in other functions such as power cuts and reconnection, alarm reporting and disconnections between other functionalities.

The Advanced Measurement Infrastructure (AMI) is today the most used infrastructure for SMS. The AMI architecture connects smart home appliances with the smart meter creating a Home Area Network (HAN). The SM is responsible for measuring the data consumed by these devices and reporting them to the electric company.

Today's SMS are bidirectional both in their communication interfaces and in energy management. The latter implies that, in addition to measuring the consumption of electrical energy, it is also possible to measure the production of electrical energy carried out in renewable generation systems (photovoltaic, wind, among others) (Ye, 2015).

The consumption reported in the SMS is reported to intermediate devices called concentrators or collectors (in some implementations of AMI they are called gateways since they allow to provide additional services such as security and privacy of the information). These concentrating devices together with the other SMS form a communication network of the medium geographical extension called Neighborhood Area Network (NAN).

The concentrators report the information of all the SMS in the HAN through the electric company in communication networks of a large geographical area such as WAN and Field Area Network (FAN).

All the information from the data concentrators reaches the end of the communications end of the electricity company, in which there is an implementation of a data center responsible, among other things, for reporting the consumption information for the billing of the consumed electrical energy. All this is done through a Measurement Data Management System (MDMS) (Al-Shaer, 2016).

In general, a SMS differs from a traditional measurement system by the use of a data communication system and a data storage system that allows automating the billing process of electricity consumption. The general architecture of AMI is shown in Figure 1.

Among the main threats of cybersecurity in AMI are: the interruption of the measurement (disconnection of the meter, deletion of the event log), investment of the meter (for less consumption data record), the deletion of records, the alteration of stored data, the interruption of communications to prevent data from being reported, the alteration of consumption data

"on the fly" when they are reported, as well as the injection of false information (for example, alteration of dynamic energy prices) and the retransmission of packets (duplicate packets) (Knapp, 2013)

Fig. 1. AMI Architecture.

SMS are embedded systems that are currently connected to the Internet and for this reason are called the Internet of Things (IoT) devices, for that reason they are also vulnerable to other types of threats such as viruses, system details operative, communication channels, both wireless and wired, among other popular incidents of IoT devices (Song, 2018).

2.1 Cryptography

The main security mechanism implemented to solve this problem lie in the use of cryptographic techniques. Cryptography allows data to be encrypted, stored, and transmitted securely. Only people with appropriate access can decipher this information.

Cryptography bases its functioning on mathematical functions and algorithms that require high computational power, making it a challenge in IoT devices and in SMS it is not the exception. For this, many works have focused on algorithms and lightweight cryptographic functions that can work properly in SG, particularly in SMS that despite being light are robust so that they are not easily decipherable (Wang et al., 2013), (Liu et al., 2017), and (Samudrala, 2017).

Hash functions are cryptographic functions that, given an input, produce a single output. This output has a predetermined size that is determined by the hash function and is not reversible; i.e. through the exit, you cannot get the entry. The hash functions serve to validate the integrity and consistency of the data, which is why they are today the most used mechanisms today to validate data integrity due to its simplicity of use and easy adaptation to IoT and SMS devices.

Like classical cryptography, many works have focused on combining hash-function schemes that allow being quick when

generating and validating information with sizes of keys large enough to guarantee the robustness of the data (Abbasinezhad-Mood et al., 2018), and (Mohammadali et al., 2018).

The main problem of cryptography is the exchange of the keys that allow decrypted the messages. The cryptography generally by its way of handling the keys has been divided into symmetric and asymmetric (Borges, 2017).

In symmetric cryptography with a single key, the message is encrypted and decrypted. The problem lies in the sharing of this key because it must preferably be done through a secure channel. To avoid this, asymmetric cryptography emerged to avoid this type of problem. Hence, two keys are generally used: a public key and a private key. When the sender wishes to send a message, it is necessary to know the public key of the recipient. These public keys can be shared without any problem. Private keys, however, need to be rigorously saved. Knowing the public key of the recipient, the sender with its public and private key encrypts the message sent to the recipient. The receiver to decipher the message occupies the public key of the issuer to verify that it was sent by this person and together with its public and private key can decrypt the message.

Due to its great advantages, asymmetric key cryptography has been widely used in security schemes such as digital signatures. To do this, you must have Certification Authorities (CA) that allows you to keep the identity certificates of each of the parties. With this arises the problem of the administration of certificates and public keys. Various mechanisms have been devised to solve it, being the most popular Public Key Infrastructure (PKI).

The problem with PKI and other public key exchange mechanisms is that as participants grow, their functioning becomes more complex, and in general, it is a centralized mechanism. For these reasons, it has become a problem for IoT and SMS devices, so that currently many research works have focused on solving this part. Other works have focused on more efficient and secure mechanisms in digital signatures (Seferian et al., 2018).

Other techniques used are digital signature schemes, Preventing and Intrusive Detection Systems (IPS and IDS) (Faisal et al., 2015). Recently, blockchain techniques (Blockchains) have been used because it is the combination of multiple cybersecurity techniques (Eyal, 2017).

3. METHODOLOGY AND RESULTS

For our study, a Single Board Computer (SBC) Raspberry Pi with the Smart Pi power monitor have considered as the best hardware solution to perform a SM (nD-enseserve, 2019). The authors consider that the Next Generation of SMs will have more capabilities for data storage and processing.

To perform the practical activities, it has been used a Raspberry Pi 3 Model B board with Raspbian operating system.

Two cryptographies suites implementations have been chosen for tests: GNU Privacy Guard (GPG, 2019) and Open Secure Socket Layer (OpenSSL, 2019), do these, are one of the most implemented cryptographic open source suites in Embedded Operating Systems such as Linux. □

In order to carry out the evaluation, a Cryptographic Use Coefficient (CUC) was determined to take into consideration the main aspects for an embedded SMS: Time of Encryption/Decryption (TED) and Memory Used for Encryption/Decryption (MUED).

$$CUC = (TED*0.5) + (MUED*0.5) \quad (1)$$

These parameters were considering due to are the most relevant characteristics in the algorithms for cybersecurity in SMS. The weights of each parameter were equal (50% per parameter) as shown in equation 1.

The dataset for testing was a set of a 20-energy transaction in the SM with a total size of 1KB. The data is a CSV text file.

All the tests were executed 1000 times and the results reported are the averages.

3.1 Time of Encryption/Decryption

In GPG suite the algorithms tested were Blowfish (Mudepalli et al., 2017), Camelia254 (Liu et al., 2016), CAST5 (Lee et al., 2014), IDEA (Yuan et al., 2014), and Twofish (Zhang et al., 2016). The selection of these algorithms is due to strength for decryption without know the key. All the algorithms are symmetric. □

In OpenSSL suite, the algorithms tested were AES-256 (Kim, 2012) and RSA-4096 (Huang et al., 2015). AES is a symmetric algorithm and RSA is asymmetric encryption algorithm.

For time measurement, the time command in Linux was used. The executed real time was considering the results. □

Table I shows the average time for encryption/decryption the transaction file using GPG suite. The times are expressed in seconds.

TABLE I. AVERAGE TIME IN GPG CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHMS

Blowfish	Camelia254	Cast5	IDEA	Twofish
5.34	3.55	4.44	3.52	3.27

Table II shows the average time for encryption/decryption of the transaction file using OpenSSL suite. The times are expressed in seconds.

TABLE II. AVERAGE TIME IN OPENSLL CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHMS

AES-256	RSA-4096 Key Generator	RSA-4096 Encryption/Decryption
17.28	6.38	1.13

3.2 Memory Used for Encryption/Decryption

For the measurement of memory for the cryptography algorithms, the authors used the top command and checked the percentage of memory used.

Table III shows the average memory use percentage in GPG cryptography algorithms.

TABLE III. AVERAGE MEMORY USE % IN GPG CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHMS

Blowfish	Camelia254	Cast5	IDEA	Twofish
5.63	7.27	9.3	11.1	13.93

Table IV shows the average memory use percentage in OpenSSL Cryptography.

TABLE IV. AVERAGE MEMORY USE % IN OPENSLL CRYPTOGRAPHY ALGORITHMS

AES-256	RSA-4096 Key Generator	RSA-4096 Encryption/Decryption
29.46	97.19	12.64

4. CONCLUSIONS

A comparison of Cryptography Algorithms for Data Analytics Application in Smart Meters has been presented.

In the literature review, AES-256 is the best algorithm of the algorithms choose in this comparative, although is the most complex algorithm in time processing. □

We can observe that the phase of generation of public keys is the one that requires a greater amount of time in the RSA algorithm, however, this phase may be necessary only during the first encryption and then reused, so that if we discard this time in the comparison the times are closer. Even so, the sum of the times used in the phases of generation of the random key, encryption of the file and encryption of the key are better than in the AES algorithm. □

The time for key generation in RSA is the most consumption of memory than other algorithms. There is not a significant difference in memory usage between algorithms. □

The strength of cryptographic algorithms is very hard and there are diverse cryptographic suites and APIs for data encryption/decryption.

The cryptographic algorithms for SMS are not in real time (the AMI average time for sending data is 15 minutes). If the applications need more efficient real-time algorithms, it will be necessary a hardware implementation of cryptography algorithms or using a Real-Time Operating System with high priorities for data encryption/decryption. □

Data Analytics applications are in two types: stored data and streaming data. For traditional data analytic (stored data) the selected cryptography algorithms work in a good manner but for data streaming analysis (real time) another class of cryptography must be used. □

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